

An undescribed species of *Cryptosaccus* (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) from the south-west of the province of León, NW Spain

Una nueva especie de *Cryptosaccus* (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) del sur de Province León, NO España

David T. HOLYOAK* and Geraldine A. HOLYOAK*

Recibido el 25-VIII-2013. Aceptado el 4-XI-2013

ABSTRACT

An unknown species of the family Hygromiidae, discovered among calcium-poor quartzite rocks at high altitude (ca 1879 m) on a mountain ridge in the Sierra de la Cabrera on the southern border of the province of León, is named here as *Cryptosaccus cabrerensis*. The shell characters and genital anatomy show strong similarities to *Cryptosaccus asturiensis* Prieto & Puente, 1994, as well as some clear differences. The new species has the accessory sac adjoining the dart sac visible externally during dissection, unlike *C. asturiensis*. Possible affinities of *Cryptosaccus* with other genera are discussed.

RESUMEN

Se describe una especie desconocida de la familia Hygromiidae, descubierta entre roquedos de cuarcita pobre en calcio, a gran altura (ca 1879 m) en una montaña en la Sierra de la Cabrera en la frontera sur de la provincia de León, bajo el nombre *Cryptosaccus cabrerensis*. Los caracteres de la concha y la anatomía del aparato genital muestran una fuerte similitud con *Cryptosaccus asturiensis* Prieto y Puente, 1994, así como algunas diferencias claras. La nueva especie tiene el saco accesorio junto al saco de dardo visible externamente durante la disección, a diferencia de *C. asturiensis*. Se discuten las posibles afinidades de *Cryptosaccus* con otros géneros.

INTRODUCTION

Cryptosaccus asturiensis was named in a new monotypic genus by PRIETO & PUENTE (1994) from rocky limestone habitats in the Somiedo Valley of Asturias province, NW. Spain, where it appears to be a localised endemic. In July 2013 an unknown species of Hygromiidae was found by the authors among calcium-poor quartzite rocks at high altitude (ca 1879 m) on a mountain ridge of the Sierra de la Cabrera on the south-

hern border of León province. This did not match any of the species listed for León province or adjoining Zamora province in the comprehensive review by HERMIDA (1992). Investigation of its shell characters and genital anatomy have revealed strong similarities to *Cryptosaccus asturiensis* as well as some clear differences, so it is described here and named as a second species of the genus, *C. cabrerensis*.

* Quinta da Cachopa, Barcoila, 6100-014 Cabeçudo, Portugal. e-mail: holyoak9187@gmail.com

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Grid references of localities were obtained using hand-held Garmin GPS devices, in 2007 using a GPS 12 accurate to <10 m horizontally but considerably less accurate for altitudinal data, in 2013 using an Etrex High Sensitivity instrument accurate to <5 m both horizontally and vertically. Living snails were drowned in water overnight, then preserved in 80% Industrial Methylated Spirit.

Shells of the new species described below are weakly calcified, so they are remarkably thin, flexible and fragile. Hence, many of the empty shells are broken or distorted and measurement data are partly incomplete for that reason. Other shell measurements are incomplete because they are based on whole drowned specimens retained in spirit, with which the presence of the extended body prevents measurements of the aperture and umbilicus. It proved to be impossible to pull intact bodies from the shells of this taxon without destroying the shell, so that the anatomical material studied was limited to foreparts of four bodies that could be extracted, in three of them by making a hole in the underside of the penultimate

shell whorl in order to cut through the body. Other specimens were left intact in spirit to allow future studies. Extraction of more of the body from the more calcified shells of *C. asturiensis* did not present any difficulty. Shell descriptions and dissections were carried out using a Meiji RZ Series stereo-microscope, drawings were made with assistance from a Meiji drawing tube, shell photographs with an Infinity1 camera and shell measurements were made with an eye-piece graticule. Shell whorls were counted using the method described by KERNEY & CAMERON (1979). Proximal and distal refer to the position in relation to the ovotestis.

Abbreviations: AH: maximum height of shell aperture; AW: maximum width of shell aperture; B: shell breadth; CGAH: Collection of G.A. and D.T. Holyoak; DTH: D.T. Holyoak; GAH: G.A. Holyoak; H: shell height; IMS: Industrial Methylated Spirit; MNCN: Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid; n: sample size; NHMUK: The Natural History Museum, London; U: maximum width of umbilicus. The map references for localities are based on the U.T.M. grid. The material described is in CGAH, MNCN and NHMUK.

TAXONOMIC PART & RESULTS

HYGROMIIDAE Tryon, 1866

Cryptosaccus Prieto & Puente, 1994; type species *C. asturiensis* Prieto & Puente, 1994 by original designation

Cryptosaccus asturiensis Prieto & Puente, 1994

Cryptosaccus asturiensis Prieto & Puente, 1994, Arch. Moll., 123: 112. [Type locality: 2 km al sur de Pola de Somiedo, en la base de la pared de un contrafuerte calcáreo. PRIETO, PUENTE, ALTONAGA & GÓMEZ-MOLINER (2011: 878) pointed out that this was "entre Caunedo y Gúa" and that the UTM coordinates originally given as 29T QH 234 772 do not represent the type locality].

Material examined: Specimens all from Spain, in CGAH: (a) by AS227 N. of Pola de Somiedo, Prov. Asturias, 29T QH 232 769, E.-facing limestone crag and slopes, ca 655 m alt., 23 May 2007, GAH & DTH site E23, 1 dry shell & body in IMS, 13 specimens in IMS; (b) just E. of AS227 at ca 3 km S. of Santa Maria del Puerto, León province, 29T QH 261 655, limestone rocks and grassland on W.-facing slope, ca 1410 m alt., 25 & 26 May 2007, DTH site E27, dry shell & body in IMS, 2 specimens in IMS, 13 shells (dead when collected).

Figure 1. Shells of *Cryptosaccus cabrerensis* sp. nov. A-C: holotype (shell breadth 7.8 mm). D-F: paratypes from type locality. D: apical whorls to show microsculpture; E: “scaly” microsculpture on periphery of body whorl near aperture (to left of photograph); F: living animal aestivating on underside of quartzite boulder (shell breadth ca 7.5 mm).

Figura 1. Conchas de Cryptosaccus cabrerensis spec nov. A-C: holotipo (ancho de la concha 7,8 mm); D-F: paratipos de la localidad tipo. D: vueltas apicales mostrando la microescultura; E: microescultura “escamosa” en la periferia de la última vuelta, cerca de la apertura (a la izquierda de la fotografía); F: animal vivo en estivación en la parte inferior de un bloque de cuarcita (ancho de la concha, unos 7,5 mm).

When the species was named it was known only from the type locality, from steep limestone crags. PRIETO *ET AL.* (2011: 878) added three more localities, all within the Somiedo Valley, including a limestone wall and a road cutting. A “Vulnerable” Red List category is assigned to the species

(GOMEZ, 2011; PRIETO *ET AL.*, 2011). Our site (b) listed above apparently represents a significant extension to the published data on the geographical and altitudinal ranges and recorded habitat of the species and the first record of it (just) outside the Somiedo Valley and (just) in León province.

Cryptosaccus cabrerensis G.A. Holyoak & D.T. Holyoak sp. nov.

Type material: Holotype (Figs 1A-C; reg. no. MNCN15.05/60087) from type locality, collected 1 July 2013 by G.A. Holyoak and D.T. Holyoak at site E334; forepart of body in spirit (IMS) and dry shell kept separately.

Paratypes: All from type locality with same collection data as holotype; 3 shells (dry) and incomplete bodies (foreparts in IMS), 5 specimens in IMS, 18 shells (dead when collected, mainly in poor condition) in CGAH; 1 specimen in absolute ethanol in NHMUK.

Type locality: ca 1 km W. of pass at Alto del Peñón (Sierra de la Cabrera, León province, Spain), 29T QG 0178 7555, ca 1879 m alt., unshaded quartzite scree adjoining low scrub high on N.-facing slope.

Etymology: PRIETO & PUENTE (1994: 110) stated that the generic name *Cryptosaccus* was derived from the greek *kryptos* = oculto (hidden) and the latin *saccus* = saco (sac). Our species epithet *cabrerensis* is an adjective derived from Sierra de la Cabrera, the massif around the type locality. *Saccus* is a masculine noun and the latin suffix *-ensis* is in agreement with the generic name for the epithets *cabrerensis* and *asturiensis*.

Figure 2. Anatomy of distal genitalia in *Cryptosaccus cabrerensis* sp. nov. A: holotype; B: partly schematic diagram of penis, vagina and dart sac complex in a paratype (showing longitudinal sections of dart sac complex and distal two-thirds of penis; the vagina and genital atrium opened and flattened to illustrate internal ridges). Abbreviations, as: accessory sac; bc: bursa copulatrix; dbc: duct of bursa copulatrix; ds: dart sac; e: epiphallus; f: flagellum; fo: free oviduct; ga: genital atrium; gp: genital pore; mg: mucus gland; p: penis; prm: penial retractor muscle; ror: right ommatophore retractor muscle; sod: spermoviduct; v: vagina; vd: vas deferens; ve: verge.

Figura 2. Anatomía de los órganos genitales distales en *Cryptosaccus cabrerensis* spec. nov. A: holotipo; B: diagrama semiesquemático del pene, la vagina y complejo del saco del dardo en una paratipo (mostrando secciones longitudinales de complejo del saco del dardo y de los dos tercios distales de pene; la vagina y el atrio genital abiertos y aplastados para mostrar las crestas internas). Abreviaturas, as: saco accesorio; bc: bolsa copulatrix; dbc: conducto de la bolsa copulatrix; ds: saco del dardo; e: epifalo; f: flagelo; fo: oviducto libre; ga: atrio genital; gp: poro genital; mg: glándula del mucus; p: pene; prm: músculo retractor del pene; ror: músculo retractor del ommatoforo derecho; sod: spermoviduct; v: vagina; vd: vaso deferente; ve: verga.

Description: Adult shell (Figs 1A-F) very depressed conical with flatter apex and somewhat flattened below. Breadth at maturity 6.9-7.9 mm (n = 10), height 3.4-4.5 mm (n = 9), H/B 0.49-0.61 (n = 9). Whorls 4.5-4.8 (n = 9), expanding regularly, rounded at periphery, distinctly flattened above, with moderately deep sutures. Umbilicus narrow, maximum width 0.7-1.1 mm (n = 4) (U/B 0.10-0.14, n = 4), deep and symmetrical, exposing inner edges of uppermost whorls. Aperture rounded-oval except where interrupted by penultimate whorl, slightly

flattened below, maximum width 3.0-3.8 mm (n = 5), maximum height 2.7-3.5 mm (n = 6) (AW / AH 1.10-1.18, n = 5). Aperture lacking any internal rib; peristome thin throughout, plane except at umbilicus where narrowly reflected. Shell very thin, uncalcified, flexible when fresh, translucent, light brownish-green.

Shell surface with waxy lustre. Protoconch nearly smooth. Whorl 1.0-1.5 with distinct, regular, spiral ridges (Fig. 1D), which become much less obvious amongst other sculpture on later whorls. Irregular low transverse ribs or

striae (growth ridges) ± prominent from whorl 1.3 to shell aperture, these tending to be more strongly developed on top of shell in narrow band below each suture. Penultimate and body whorls with microsculpture on perior-tracum of closely spaced, shallowly crescentic transverse ridges giving a scaly pattern (their sides concave towards shell aperture: Fig. 1E), arranged in somewhat irregular spiral rows; these are absent from umbilicus and a broad zone around it on underside of shell. Shell hairs apparently lacking, but small immatures not seen.

Exterior of body with foreparts light grey above and towards foot-fringe, sides and sole of foot whitish; mantle whitish with irregular blotches and large spots of dark brown, these markings larger and darker (blackish) near right-hand edge, forming irregular lines. The dark markings are visible on living animals through the translucent shell (Fig. 1F).

Genital anatomy (Fig. 2), based on dissection of distal parts of bodies of four mature individuals: Genital pore located close behind lower tentacle on right-hand side of forepart of body at about mid-height. Genital atrium short, its proximal end of similar width to vagina, narrowing distally towards genital pore. Right ommatophore retractor muscle passes between penis and vagina. Penis moderately long, cylindrical, with penial retractor muscle inserted at its proximal end, the muscle short and wide to narrower and moderately long (two-thirds length of epiphallus), attached to body wall. Interior of penis studied in one specimen: distal two-thirds of penis comprised of an outer sheath that joins genital atrium at its narrower distal end; most of interior of sheath occupied by long-conical verge that tapers to a bluntly pointed tip at distal end, which has a large pore. Epiphallus long, the proximal part coiled. Flagellum long (up to 1.5× length of epiphallus), conical-cylindrical, in three individuals coiled on top of epiphallus when *in situ*, in fourth individual extended proximally inside body wall. Vas deferens a thin tube, ending at junction of epiphallus and flage-

llum, passing distally closely attached alongside epiphallus and penis to penial-vaginal angle (beneath right ommatophore retractor muscle), then returning proximally alongside vagina (beneath two mucus glands) and free oviduct. Vagina ± cylindrical, of similar length to penis but often somewhat wider, with large dart sac complex inserting externally at point about one-third below its proximal end. Inner wall of vagina (one examined) with nine high ridges that continue distally to middle of vagina; several ridges coalesce in distal one-third of vagina, leaving five or six ridges at its distal end, two of which continue along interior of outer part of genital atrium. The dart sac complex clearly a double structure when viewed externally, with outer part (dart sac) 2.5× width and of greater length than inner part (accessory sac). Dart sac muscular; one examined internally containing small dart (two broken white cylindrical pieces seen: *ca* 0.25 and 0.2 mm long, both of *ca* 0.05 mm diameter); narrow central canal of sac opens into vagina in a longitudinally elongate pore. The accessory sac not fused to adjacent wall of vagina for much of its length and free from dart sac for about one-half of its length, also muscular, with narrow central cavity (empty in one dissected) that opens as pore into vagina. Six, seven or eight mucus glands in four groups insert near proximal end of vagina; in one individual two groups each of two pairs arise on opposite sides of vagina, in other individuals one or two of glands not paired and their arrangement around vagina rather variable. All mucus glands short, narrowed at insertion and widening to a swollen bulbous proximal end. Free oviduct cylindrical, similar in thickness to vagina but about one-third its length. Duct of bursa copulatrix cylindrical, moderately wide throughout, nearly twice length of vagina and nearly as wide, coiled *in situ*. Bursa copulatrix thin-walled, closely appressed to and resting within curve of spermo-viduct, in three individuals D-shaped with duct inserting obliquely on the rounded edge, in one individual oval but tapering into duct.

DISCUSSION

C. cabrerensis differs conspicuously from *C. asturiensis* in shell characters. Its shell is smaller (breadth up to 7.9 mm compared to 10 mm), with fewer whorls (up to 4.8 compared to 5.5-6), much thinner and more translucent, and the sculpture of projecting triangular scales on the periphery of the body whorl is much lower and less developed. Their genital anatomy is generally similar, differing most obviously in the dart sac of *C. cabrerensis* being accompanied by a smaller accessory sac that is visible externally during dissection, whereas in *C. asturiensis* the accessory sac is not visible externally, this character having formed the basis of the generic name *Cryptosaccus*. Also, the bursa copulatrix is much more elongate in *C. asturiensis* (length $>5\times$ width) than in *C. cabrerensis* (length $1-2\times$ width).

Although the specific distinctness of *C. cabrerensis* from *C. asturiensis* can hardly be doubted, they nevertheless appear to be more closely related to each other than to any other Hygromiidae. Thus, they share a shell of similar general form, narrowly umbilicated with a simple peristome and with distinctive scale-like sculpture on the periphery of the body whorl. Among characters of the genital anatomy, they share a single dart sac with a small accessory sac joined along its inner edge, six to eight mucus glands inserting proximally to the insertion of the dart sac arranged approximately as two pairs each on opposite sides of the vagina, a long slender epiphallus and a long slender flagellum. They are also both rupestral species occurring in adjacent regions of NW. Spain, albeit separated by virtually the full width of León province (Fig. 3).

PRIETO & PUENTE (1994) pointed out the considerable biogeographic and ecological similarities between *Cryptosaccus asturiensis* and *Pyrenaearia* spp. However, they did not emphasise the close similarity between them in most characters of their genital anatomy, perhaps because *Pyrenaearia* differs in having the acces-

sory sac visibly separate from the dart sac externally, often having the mucus glands inserting closer to the insertion of the dart sac, in addition to differences in shell sculpture (lack of scaly microsculpture; juveniles often with shell hairs). Nevertheless, since *C. cabrerensis* has an accessory sac that is visible externally, it prompts reconsideration of possible affinities with *Pyrenaearia*. A recent molecular-phylogenetic study of *Pyrenaearia* (ELEJALDE, MADEIRA, PRIETO, BACKELJAU & GÓMEZ-MOLINER, 2009) did not consider *Cryptosaccus*, but its detailed analytical data should now provide an excellent basis for future comparisons. Since *Zenobiella subrufescens* (Miller, 1822) also has similar genital anatomy (SCHILEYKO, 2005: 1961), a "scaly" pattern of shell microsculpture and a range extending to N. Spain it should also be compared, although its shell differs in having a very small umbilicus.

C. cabrerensis is known only from the type locality, on an exposed, gently N-facing montane slope at ca 1879 m alt., close below a rocky ridge that forms a major watershed which represents the border between Province León and Province Zamora to the south (Fig. 3). The snails were concealed beneath the surface of an unshaded scree composed of boulders and large blocks of quartzite (Fig. 4). Most of them were close to the upper edge of the scree adjacent to dense low scrub (<0.5 m high), comprised of *Genista sanabrensis* Valdés Berm., Castrov. & Casaseca (the commonest bush), *Vaccinium myrtillus* L. and *Festuca* sp. with *Erica australis* L. ca 1 m high nearby. The flora and rock type indicate extremely calcium-poor conditions, with acidic soils.

Living *C. cabrerensis* occurred at low density, aestivating in the hot dry sunny weather mainly on the undersides of rocks (Fig. 1F); they had a thin membranous and translucent epiphragm inside the shell aperture. The only other mollusc we found there was a single dead shell of *Oxychilus* cf. *alliaris* (Miller, 1822).

Figure 3. Map of north-western Spain showing distribution of *Cryptosaccus asturiensis* and *C. cabrerensis* sp. nov. in ten kilometre squares of the U.T.M. grid. Figure 4. Habitat of *Cryptosaccus cabrerensis* spec. nov. at the type locality.

Figura 3. Mapa del noroeste de España indicando la distribución de *Cryptosaccus asturiensis* y de *C. cabrerensis* sp. nov. en cuadrículas U.T.M. de 10 km. Figura 4. Hábitat de *Cryptosaccus cabrerensis* spec. nov. en la localidad tipo.

Discovery of an undescribed species of *Cryptosaccus* among acidic rocks at such high elevation was unexpected. More widespread searching in the Sierra de la Cabrera and beyond will be needed to establish its range and conservation status.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ELEJALDE M.A., MADEIRA M.J., PRIETO C.E., BACKELJAU T. & GÓMEZ-MOLINER B.J. 2009. Molecular phylogeny, taxonomy, and evolution of the land snail genus *Pyrenaearia* (Gastropoda, Helicoidea). *American Malacological Bulletin*, 27 (1/2): 69-81.
- GÓMEZ B. 2011. *Cryptosaccus asturiensis*. In: IUCN 2013. IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Version 2013.1. <www.iucn. red-list.org>. Downloaded 21 August 2013.
- HERMIDA J. 1992. *Estudios faunísticos y ecológicos de los moluscos gasterópodos terrestres de Asturias, León, Zamora y Salamanca*. Unpublished doctoral thesis, Departamento de Biología Animal, Universidad de Santiago de Compostela. 302 pp.
- KERNEY M.P. & CAMERON R.A.D. 1979. *Land snails of Britain & north-west Europe*. London: HarperCollins. 288 pp., 24 pls.
- PRIETO C.E. & PUENTE A.I. 1994. Un nuevo Hygromiinae del Norte de la Península Ibérica, *Cryptosaccus asturiensis* n. gen., n. sp. *Archiv für Molluskenkunde*, 123 (1/6): 109-122.
- PRIETO C.E., PUENTE A.I., ALTONAGA K. & GÓMEZ-MOLINER B.J. 2011. *Cryptosaccus asturiensis* Prieto y Puente, 1994. In: VERDÚ J.R. *Atlas y Libro Rojo de los invertebrados amenazados de España. Especies Vulnerables. Volumen 2: Moluscos*. Madrid: Editorial Ministerio de Medio Ambiente Rural y Marino, pp. 877-880.
- SCHILEYKO A.A. 2005. Treatise on recent terrestrial pulmonate molluscs. Part 14. Helicodontidae, Ciliellidae, Hygromiidae. *Rutshenica, Suppl.*, Moscow, 2: 1907-2047.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Thanks are due to Rui da Costa Mendes for help with literature. Fig. 3 was prepared using the DMAP software written by Dr A.J. Morton.